

PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

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Prepared by: Elisa Tronconi (Astir), Stefania Occhipinti (Astir), Felice Catania (Astir)

Revised by: Guido Bertolini (IRFMN), Chiara Pandolfini (IRFMN), Giulia Irene Ghilardi (IRFMN)

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
AOT	Ahead-Of-Time
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BFF	Back-end-for-Front end
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
EC2	Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud
eCREAM	Enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction
ED	Emergency Department
EHR	Electronic health record
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GB	Giga Byte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HBP	Human Brain Project
HL7	Health Level Seven
HMAC	Hash-based Message Authentication Code
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IdM	Identity Manager
IRFMN	Istituto Di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Italy
JIT	Just-In-Time
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLMs	Large Language Models
MIP	Medical Information Platform
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OAuth2	Open Authorization 2.0
OIDC	OpenID Connect
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SFTP	SSH File Transfer Protocol
SPAs	Single-Page Application
SSH	Secure Shell
TLoC	Transient Loss of Consciousness
TXT	Text
UC1	Use Case 1
UC2	Use Case 2
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WAF	Web Application Firewall
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document outlines the progress in developing the eCREAM integrated platform under Work Package 6 (WP6). The primary goal of WP6 is to create a unified platform that integrates various eCREAM modules, including interfaces with hospitals, Natural Language Processing (NLP), semantic transformation, translations, and data analysis. The platform will also ensure consistency in localizing eCREAM tools across different countries, functioning as a central hub for all the project activities modules.

The activities described in this deliverable concern the finalization of the platform infrastructure, implementation of key modules, and preparation for the actual installation of the integrated eCREAM platform.

Overall, WP6 is progressing as planned, with significant advancements in the design and technical development of the eCREAM platform, laying a strong foundation for future project phases.

Introduction

This report presents the progress made in the eCREAM integrated platform's architecture design activity.

The design elements will be reported below. The document also includes a summary of task 6.4, which covers the installation of the platform's infrastructure and modules.

Objectives of WP6

WP6 is dedicated to developing a transversal module (i.e. Translation Manager) that ensures the alignment of all translations necessary for localizing various eCREAM tools across participating countries. Additionally, WP6 integrates all the eCREAM modules (interfaces with hospitals, NLP, semantic transformation, translations, and data analysis) into a coherent information system.

Specifically, WP6 aims to:

- Develop the Translation Manager to function across all eCREAM modules
- Design the architecture of the eCREAM integrated platform
- Provide the infrastructure required for the implementation of the eCREAM integrated platform
- Implement internal interfaces.

Platform architecture design

1. Functional requirements

In D6.2, the overall functionality of the eCREAM platform, divided into Local and Central components, had been described as follows:

- **eCREAM Local:** installed at hospitals' level, it collects and extracts variables from hospital data systems to build the eCREAM dataset. It also manages data preprocessing and transmission to the Central eCREAM component
- **eCREAM Central:** it organises and stores data in two distinct database schemas dedicated to Use Case 1 (UC1) and Use Case 2 (UC2). UC1 focuses on developing models to calculate the propensity to hospitalisation, while UC2 aims to develop dashboards for citizens, ED staff, and policymakers.

Figure 1 - eCREAM platform

Within the platform, cross components were described at both the central and local levels.

Cross components of the eCREAM Central:

- API Authentication
- MySQL
- Translation Manager

Cross components of the Local eCREAM:

- eCREAM Hospital Client
- Anonymization tool
- MySQL
- Normalisation tool

2. Principles followed

The architectural design principles followed are:

- **Modularity:** The choice was made to divide the system into smaller modules with well-defined goals but contributing to a specific function within the overall architecture. Modularity makes maintenance of individual components more agile since each one can be managed separately.
- **Independency of the modules:** Each module functions independently, without depending directly on the others, allowing a single module to be developed, updated, or replaced for maintenance and upgrade activities, limiting the risk of errors.
- **Minimal coupling of the modules:** Minimal coupling ensures that modules interact with each other only when necessary and in a manner conveyed through well-defined interfaces. This reduces complexity and makes maintenance more agile because each module has minimal impact on the others. The platform uses REST and HTTPS API interfaces for communication between modules, which reduces the degree of coupling between them. Modules can then communicate via standardized protocols without depending directly on each other.
- **Data centricity:** Data is placed at the centre of the architecture by adopting a common data model that all modules can insist on. Integrity is fundamental to all system operations and decisions and is ensured using the MySQL database, allowing the various modules to interact with the data.

Integration with the New ED-EHR system is via the HL7 FHIR standard, further reinforcing the concept of data centrality.

- **Lego-like architecture:** modules can be combined and integrated easily like Lego bricks. This feature allows great flexibility in building or modifying the system by adding, removing, or replacing modules without compromising the entire system. The modular and flexible nature of components such as the API Service repository, which can accept new API services or modules, highlights the idea of a “Lego-like” architecture. The Lego-like approach promotes reusability and adaptability of components. New features can be integrated without the need to restructure the entire platform.
- **Isolation of data:** Communications with external sources are through defined interfaces, thus protecting the integrity of the system and internal data by preventing vulnerability from direct interactions with external sources and monitoring access control, improving the overall security of the system. Communication with external sources, such as external clients and the SFTP server, is via HTTPS and API, ensuring the isolation of internal data. This creates a protective barrier, ensuring that data is not directly exposed to unauthorized sources.

Interoperability is ensured using APIs and open standards (e.g., JSON), tools for decoupling and dispatching, in compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), making data easily findable and reusable. Compatible analytical tools, alongside adherence to security and privacy regulations, including GDPR compliance, ensure that data access is restricted, traceable, and protected through access management systems and data anonymization techniques.

Following the definition of functional and non-functional requirements, the next step is the architectural design phase. This phase serves as a bridge between analysis and implementation, enabling the translation of requirements into a coherent, scalable, and maintainable technical structure. The following chapter presents the key architectural decisions, outlining the design rationale and the role of each component within the overall system architecture.

3. Architectural Design

This section presents the architectural design of the eCREAM central software platform. The main objective of this architecture is to provide a robust, scalable, and flexible foundation for the development and implementation of all future eCREAM modules and services.

The platform is designed to support a wide range of functionalities while ensuring high availability, security, and optimal performance. Key components, their interactions, and the design principles guiding the realization of this architecture will be explored. This design aims to facilitate technical understanding for developers, operational teams, and stakeholders, promoting a systematic approach to building and evolving our software ecosystem.

The architectural design of the central eCREAM platform distinguishes between:

- **Client Applications:** These modules reside externally to the central platform and interact with it by consuming the exposed services. They represent user interfaces or other applications that require the functionalities and data managed by the platform.
- **Modules Hosted by the Central Platform:** These modules are an integral part of the platform and reside within its environment. They provide the core services and functionalities that are then exposed to the client modules.

This division ensures a clear separation of responsibilities and facilitates system scalability and maintainability. Client modules focus on presentation logic or integration, while the central platform manages business logic, data persistence, and security.

Figure 2 - AWS: cloud delivery of the eCREAM platform

AWS has been selected for the cloud delivery of the eCREAM platform. The delivery of the eCREAM platform via Amazon Web Services (AWS) offers numerous strategic advantages that contribute to the overall robustness, scalability, and flexibility of the system. The choice of AWS as a cloud computing provider aligns perfectly with eCREAM’s architectural objectives of ensuring high availability, security, and optimal performance.

Scalability and Elasticity:

AWS offers almost unlimited scalability, allowing the eCREAM platform to dynamically adapt to load requirements. This means that resources can be automatically increased or decreased based on demand, ensuring that the system can handle traffic peaks without interruptions and optimizing operational costs.

Reliability and Availability:

The global AWS infrastructure is designed for high availability. With multiple regions and availability zones, the eCREAM platform can be deployed in a way that withstands failures at the single zone or region level, ensuring almost uninterrupted operational continuity and minimizing downtime.

Security:

AWS provides a wide range of security services covering network, compute, storage, and databases. These services include identity and access management (IAM), DDoS protection (Shield), data encryption, and compliance with numerous global security standards. This allows for building a highly secure platform, protecting sensitive data, and ensuring privacy.

Wide Range of Managed Services:

AWS offers a vast array of managed services (databases, caching, message queues, serverless functions, machine learning, etc.) that can be easily integrated into the eCREAM platform. This accelerates

development, reduces the operational burden for management teams, and allows focus on core business logic rather than underlying infrastructure management.

Resilience and Disaster Recovery:

The backup, restore, and disaster recovery capabilities offered by AWS allow for the implementation of robust strategies for data protection and recovery in case of unforeseen events. This ensures the platform's resilience and the ability to quickly recover from any disruptions.

The following paragraphs describe in detail the modules constituting the central platform's architectural design. Its purpose is to furnish a comprehensive understanding of each component's functionalities, interactions, and responsibilities, elucidating their contribution to the system's overall robustness, scalability, and efficiency. The underlying logic of each module, the technologies employed for their implementation, and their interfacing mechanisms will be explored to ensure coherent data flow and optimal operational management.

Once the description of the application modules is complete, a proposal for a physical delivery architecture based on the components available within the AWS delivery environment will be provided; this proposal can be refined as the project progresses.

3.1 Client application

This section offers a detailed architectural analysis of the client applications that interact with the eCREAM central platform, as illustrated in the architecture diagram. For each application, the analysis includes:

- **Involved Central Platform Modules:** The central platform modules, to which each client application connects and on which it depends for its functionalities, are specifically listed and described.
- **Communication Protocol:** The communication protocols used by the client application to exchange data and interact with the central platform are specified. This could include standard protocols such as HTTP/S, WebSocket, AMQP, or proprietary protocols. The reasons behind the choice of specific protocols are also illustrated, for example, in terms of security, performance, scalability, or connection reliability.
- **Authentication Protocol and Authorized Users:** This section thoroughly describes the authentication protocol adopted by the client application to verify user identity and authorize access to the central platform's services. It details the specific protocol (e.g., OAuth2, OpenID Connect, SAML) and its implementation, including credential management, authorization verification, and authentication state maintenance. It also specifies the criteria and methods for determining which users are authorized to use the application, encompassing user roles, access levels, and any relevant authorization policies.

3.1.1 Translation manager

The Translation Manager component is thoroughly described in the two appendices of the document "D6.2 PLATFORM FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS":

- Annex 1_D62 - eCREAM Functional Specification Translation Manager
- Annex 2_D62 - eCREAM User Manual Translation Manager

The "Translation Manager" application exposes its functionalities through a WEB interface accessed via the HTTPS protocol. The application internally manages its users.

Figure 3 - AWS Translation Manager

A dedicated and controlled environment will be established for the component’s delivery and integration. This area will be physically and logically separated from other operational zones, ensuring a confined space with stringent access controls. Furthermore, the network infrastructure within this area will be isolated and configured with advanced firewall rules, intrusion detection systems, and regular vulnerability assessments to safeguard against unauthorized access and potential cyber threats. This approach guarantees the component’s integrity, confidentiality, and availability throughout its deployment lifecycle.

3.1.2 eCREAM Local

The eCREAM Local application represents the module for extracting and processing hospital data related to UC1 and UC2.

Document D2.2 “TESTING OF eCREAM INTERFACE MODULES” provides a detailed description of the application design and module architecture, delving into the phases of hospital data retrieval, anonymization, eCREAM model transformation, and local storage.

This paragraph contains a detailed analysis of the technical aspects concerning the processing and transmission of hospital data to the central module, specifically:

- **Authentication Protocol:** Data security is an absolute priority. The authentication protocol ensures that only authorized entities can access and transmit data to the central module. This includes robust mechanisms for identity verification and credential management, preventing unauthorized access and potential privacy breaches. The choice of authentication protocol is based on industry standards that ensure maximum protection and resilience against attacks.
- **UC1 and UC2 Data Transmission Protocol:** This protocol defines how data related to use cases one and two are structured, formatted, and transmitted to the central module.

Figure 4 - UC1 and UC2 Data Transmission Protocol

Authentication protocol

The following figure describes the authentication/authorization algorithm used by the eCREAM Local component to send clinical data to the central platform. The algorithm characteristics:

- Use of the HMAC (Hash-based Message Authentication Code) protocol for authenticating individual API calls.
- eCREAM Hospital Client services do not send any passwords over the encrypted channel, but only (possibly public) identification data.
- Authentication of API calls ensures defense against possible data tampering, and robust security for the central platform. A multi-layered approach to authentication and data integrity is employed.

Figure 5 - Authentication protocol

HMAC Protocol for API Call Authentication:

Individual API calls are authenticated using the HMAC (Hash-based Message Authentication Code) protocol. This method provides a strong guarantee of authenticity and integrity for each request. When an API call is made, a unique HMAC signature is generated using a shared secret key and the request’s data. The receiving service then re-calculates the HMAC using the same secret and data. If the calculated HMAC matches the one provided in the request, it verifies that:

- The request originated from a trusted source; only parties possessing the shared secret key can generate a valid HMAC.
- The request has not been tampered with in transit; any modification to the data during transmission would result in a different HMAC generation, thus invalidating the request.

This robust authentication mechanism is crucial for protecting against unauthorized access and ensuring the reliability of data exchange between services.

Password-Free Communication for eCREAM Hospital Client Services:

A key security principle implemented for eCREAM Hospital Client services is the complete absence of password transmission over any channel, even encrypted ones. Instead of sending sensitive credentials, these services transmit only identification data, which may be public or non-sensitive. This approach significantly reduces the risk of password compromise through interception or other attacks.

This strategy contributes to a more secure system by:

- **Minimizing exposure of sensitive data:** Passwords, which are often targets for attackers, are never exposed during communication.
- **Reducing the attack surface:** Eliminating the need to transmit passwords, the system’s vulnerability to credential theft is drastically lowered.

Comprehensive Défense Against Data Tampering and Unauthorized Access:

The combination of HMAC for API call authentication and password-free communication for client services provides a comprehensive defense against various security threats.

- **Authentication of API calls:** The HMAC protocol ensures that only legitimate and authorized applications or services can interact with the platform’s APIs. This prevents unauthorized access to critical functionalities and data.
- **Defense against possible data tampering:** The integrity checks performed by HMAC ensure that data exchanged between services remains unaltered from its original form. This is vital for maintaining the accuracy and reliability of information, especially in a hospital environment where data integrity is paramount.

UC1 and UC2 Data Transmission Protocol

The software module described in this paragraph is dedicated to the processing and secure and efficient transmission of all data related to individual ED episodes extracted through the extraction pipeline from hospital systems.

Individual ED episode data is sent to the central eCREAM platform. Here, it is processed, transformed, and normalized to feed the information databases of the eCREAM use cases (UC1 and UC2).

The logical and application flow described in this section is schematically represented in the following figure.

Figure 6 - UC1 and UC2 Data Transmission Protocol

The sending flow is described below. It is important to note that the processing described here refers to a single episode, analysed and sent to the central platform. During the solution development, based on cost/processing time constraints, the processing strategy may be modified; an example could be the integration with the NLP platform.

The processing flow on the ED episodes database is divided into two sub-flows called:

- UC1: episodes received from feeding systems are filtered to process only episodes characterized as **Dyspnoea** or **TLoC**.
- UC2: represents the totality of episodes received from the feeding systems.

UC1 Flow

The flow named 'UC1 flow' is applied only to episodes labelled 'Dyspnoea' or 'TLoC'; to this end, a filter is applied to all eligible episodes to establish whether the episode can be classified as compliant with the 'UC1 flow'.

The filtering algorithm is dedicated to the individual ED and will be built according to the specific information and compilation rules unique to each emergency department.

To address the identified issues in the filtering solution, a Template pattern will be implemented, enabling customization and extensibility of the submission system by integrating implementations developed in collaboration with emergency room personnel.

The core benefit of adopting a template pattern lies in its ability to establish a standardized framework for the filtering process while simultaneously allowing for a highly specialized filtering strategy. This means that a common sequence of operations can be defined, providing a reliable baseline for all filtering operations. However, critical points within this template will be designated as "hooks" or "placeholders", where specific, custom implementations can be injected without altering the core structure.

Through ongoing engagement and feedback, new filtering criteria can be developed. These custom implementations can then be seamlessly integrated into the existing system by plugging them into the defined template hooks.

Once the episode's belonging to the UC1 flow is determined, the sending system applies the following operational tasks to the sending pipeline:

- Augmentation
 - All episodes selected for UC1 are enriched with additional information. This data is obtained via the NLP service and is detailed in the eCREAM data model, attached to the document: *"Annex 1_D6.3- eCREAM Augmentation of the data dictionary"*
- Security data encapsulation
 - The single episode, after being processed with the NLP flow, is prepared for sending with the data security encapsulation algorithm described in the previous paragraph
- Send protocol
 - The current module facilitates seamless communication and data exchange with the eCREAM Central module. Its primary function is the protocol's integration, which is defined and exposed through the eCREAM Central module's interface APIs.

Augmentation flow

Each ED episode is defined by metadata (the eCREAM model) and by textual elements classified by type (eight different document types, whose format is detailed in the eCREAM model, have been identified within the eCREAM project).

The “Augmentation” process uses NLP services to extract coded data from the set of textual elements referring to a single EDepisode.

Figure 7 - Augmentation process

These data, combined with the initial eCREAM model, form the final model that is sent to the central platform, constituting the database for UC1.

UC2 Flow

Use case 2 involves the development of a multifunctional dashboard for monitoring the ED situation using administrative/logistical data in addition to visits, treatments, tests, etc., without any reference to the patient’s personal identifiers.

The one called “UC2 flow” is applied to all episodes in the system.

The sending system applies the following operational tasks to the sending pipeline:

- Aggregation:
 - The UC2 flow includes all episodes collected during the analysis period. The information must present aggregated data on different analysis dimensions, preventing any identification of the single case. To achieve this goal, the submission pipeline includes aggregation tasks based on the dimensions defined during the analysis and design phase of the dashboard application. The application design, conceived according to the template method pattern, represents a flexible and modular architecture. This approach will allow the configurable integration of a heterogeneous set of AWS Lambda functions. These functions, dynamically called by the core aggregation module, will have the task of processing and transforming the raw data from individual ED episodes to produce the desired dataset.
- Security data encapsulation
 - The single episode, after being processed with the NLP flow, is prepared for sending, with the data security encapsulation algorithm described in the previous paragraph.
- Send protocol

- The current module is designed to facilitate seamless communication and data exchange with the eCREAM Central module. Its primary function is to implement the integration protocol, which is defined and exposed through the eCREAM Central module’s interface APIs.

3.1.3 Dashboard

The “Dashboard” application provides a global view of all Emergency Department data, producing a series of indicators such as:

- Early warning: Parameters that indicate critical situations involving ED, such as crowding levels, boarding, and epidemiological thresholds exceeding critical values.
- EDs monitoring: Key performance indicators related to the ED department: patient flow, response times, etc.
- Epidemiological monitoring: Useful for monitoring the number of cases of specific epidemics, such as COVID or the flu.

Figure 8 - Dashboard

System access will be guaranteed through an intuitive and responsive **web interface**, designed to be fully compatible with all modern browsers (such as Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Apple Safari, and Microsoft Edge). The user interface will be developed following the latest usability and design standards, ensuring a fluid and seamless experience, regardless of the device or screen resolution.

Security and authentication will be managed via an Authentication Server, which will operate in collaboration with the Identity Manager (IdM) and Token Manager services. All application users will be registered in the IdM service. To protect application functionalities, the OIDC (OpenID Connect) Access Token protocol will be used. These tokens are not simple credentials, but an advanced mechanism for authentication and authorization.

All application functionalities will be exposed via dedicated APIs, managed by the server component. These APIs will be conveyed through the AWS API Gateway service and protected by the AWS WAF component.

Dashboard front-end

The application’s front-end dashboard represents the main user interface through which they interact with the system. This component will be entirely developed using Angular, an open-source Typescript framework

maintained by Google, known for its robustness, scalability, and rapid development capabilities for single-page applications (SPAs). Adopting Angular ensures a fluid and responsive user experience, with dynamic content updates and no need to reload the entire page. A NodeJS server is used to deliver this front-end to end-users.

Figure 9 - Dashboard front-end

Angular Material will be adopted for the creation of graphical components and to ensure a consistent and high-quality User Experience (UX). This framework, based on Google’s Material Design principles, will provide a complete library of pre-built and stylized UI components, allowing for rapid development and simplified maintenance.

Data visualization, a crucial aspect for analysis and monitoring, will be managed through the integration of Chart.js. This lightweight and versatile JavaScript library will allow the creation of a wide range of interactive and customizable charts, including bar, line, pie, and scatter charts. Integration with Angular will allow for dynamic updates of charts based on real-time data or user interactions, offering a clear and intuitive representation of information.

Management and visualization of spatial data on maps will be implemented through the open-source OpenStreetMap framework with LeafletJS.

OpenStreetMap (OSM) serves as the primary cartographic base, providing a vast archive of freely editable and usable geographic data. The use of OSM allows us to benefit from a flexible, scalable, and open-source cartographic resource.

The integration of LeafletJS with OpenStreetMap allows for:

- Displaying spatial data: Effectively loading and showing a wide variety of geographic data on OpenStreetMap layers.
- Interacting with maps: Offering users zoom, panning, area selection, and element querying functionalities.
- Customizing the interface: Adapting the appearance and behaviour of maps to the specific needs of the application, including the choice of different cartographic styles and the addition of custom controls.

- Managing multiple layers: Overlaying different data layers (e.g., points of interest, administrative boundaries, transport networks) for complex and layered analysis.

3.1.4 App for citizens

The dashboard for citizens will support them in choosing the most appropriate Emergency Department (ED) or, alternatively, a more efficient healthcare service.

A secondary objective of the study is to assess the perceived usefulness and appropriateness of the dashboards by the end-users. This evaluation will be conducted using retrospective data extracted from hospital information systems, as real-time integration with data flows from the participating facilities is beyond the scope of the current study.

Figure 10 - Citizens' app

The citizens' App will be developed as a native mobile application for Android and iOS. It will be distributed through the Play Store for Android and the Apple Store for iOS.

All functions usable from the citizens' App will be made available by the API module described in paragraph 3.2.3.

For the development of the native mobile app, the Flutter development framework was chosen, a strategic decision that offers numerous advantages in terms of efficiency, performance and maintainability. Flutter, developed by Google, allows the creation of native applications for iOS and Android from a single codebase, significantly reducing development times and costs.

Figure 11 - Flutter development framework

Flutter uses Dart as its programming language. Dart, developed by Google, is a modern, versatile and powerful programming language. Characterized by strong typing, it supports both AOT (Ahead-Of-Time) and JIT (Just-In-Time) compilation and is object-oriented.

Unlike other WebView-based cross-platform solutions, Flutter compiles Dart code directly into ARM (or x86) machine code, allowing the app to perform like apps written in Swift/Kotlin/Java. This means smooth animations at 60-120 fps and fast loading times.

This choice guarantees a consistent and high-performing user experience on both platforms, thanks to the direct rendering of graphical widgets, which eliminates the need for JavaScript bridges and improves interface fluidity.

Furthermore, the richness of customizable UI components and the vast community of developers around Flutter ensure continuous support and access to innovative solutions for future evolutions of the application. The reactive and declarative nature of the framework also facilitates debugging and application state management, contributing to cleaner and more maintainable code over time.

3.1.5 ED-EHR

Detailed information on the Frontend component of the ED-EHR system is available in the document “D3.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN”. The description of the “client” components has been taken from this document.

Figure 12 - ED-EHR client component

This layer consists of two web applications:

- **admin dashboard** will enable system administrators to manage EHR custom configurations, user permissions, and general settings related to the platform’s operations (e.g., which clinical examination approach is used among the supported ones);
- an **ED dashboard** which represents the core web application intended for ED professionals. It will assist them in managing patient data, tracking their status on the waiting list, and overseeing the clinical operational aspects of the ED. The applications belonging to the front-end will either communicate directly with back-end services or via a Back-end-for-Front end (BFF) component. The BFF acts as an intermediary, providing a streamlined and well-focused interface tailored for each frontend module, thus reducing the complexity in the frontend layer.

The central infrastructure offers its functionalities to both web applications via an HTTPS access point on the application subdomain ecreamproject.eu.

Authentication and authorization functionalities are managed as described in document “D3.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN” of the modules composing the ED-EHR system.

3.1.6 MIP

eCREAM will integrate the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP), developed by the Human Brain Project (HBP, partner of the project), to federate clinical data. The MIP is a unique open-source GDPR-compliant, privacy

aware platform, currently installed in over 30 EU hospitals, which enables remote and federated analyses from datasets physically distributed in various hospitals, research centres and biobanks, without moving the data outside their original site of storage to a central repository.

Figure 13 - MIP

An integration flow has been developed to facilitate the seamless transmission of critical data to the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP) service. This process leverages the robust and widely adopted JSON/HTTPS protocol, ensuring secure, efficient, and reliable data exchange.

The data, anonymized by the eCREAM Local sending flow, will be processed by the UC1 database and transmitted to the defined access point via specific AWS Lambda functions, in the agreed format.

3.1.7 Propensity to hospitalization algorithm

The hospitalization algorithm in the “UC1 Modules – R” component is designed to estimate the probability that a patient will be admitted from the Emergency Department, using normalized clinical data collected by the central eCREAM platform.

Its main functions are:

- Pre-processing the data to create an analytical dataset.
- Developing a predictive model, primarily using decision tree algorithms, and comparing it with other methods.
- Calculating the probability of admission for each patient.
- Generating reports for each centre that compare expected and observed admissions, highlighting performance.

Everything is implemented in R, which manages analysis, modelling, and reporting.

The tool provided for creating the algorithm to calculate the propensity for hospitalization is **RStudio Server** (open-source version).

Figure 14 - Propensity to hospitalization

RStudio Server offers a web-based integrated development environment (IDE) for writing and executing R code within the application context of the server located in the central eCREAM component’s perimeter, with access to the MySQL DBMS ‘Snapshot UC1’.

Access to the service is via username/password, requested through a dedicated web form presented by RStudio Server. The service is exposed via HTTPS protocol on the ecreamproject.eu subdomain. User accounts will be nominal and configured as Linux operating system users.

3.2 eCREAM Central Platform

The central platform delivers all application services that constitute the eCREAM system. The system was designed with a modular architecture; each module is detailed in the architecture diagram and described in the following sections.

The division into distinct application modules facilitates management and maintenance. Where specified, “managed” AWS components such as RDS or Lambda Functions were used.

Data is placed at the centre of the architecture by adopting a common data model that all modules can insist on. The data layer is a fundamental component of the central platform architecture, responsible for the persistence and organization of all information. It is specifically implemented through a robust and scalable set of MySQL databases. These databases are not managed internally but are provided and managed as a service through the AWS components named Relational Database Service (RDS). Adopting AWS RDS for MySQL offers numerous significant advantages. Firstly, it ensures high data availability and durability, thanks to the automatic replication and backup functionalities provided by the service. Secondly, it greatly simplifies database administration, freeing the team from burdensome tasks such as managing the underlying infrastructure, software updates, patching, and performance monitoring.

Security is another aspect enhanced using RDS, which offers integrated functionalities for data encryption at rest and in transit, as well as options for access control and integration with other AWS security services.

Communication with external sources, such as external clients, is via HTTPS and API, ensuring the isolation of internal data.

Each service, which exposes a functionality to the previously described client systems, presents a well-defined integration API, exposed via HTTPS protocol. This represents the only permitted method for integrating external actors with the central platform.

The adoption of AWS Security Groups, specifically configured for each module of the central platform architecture, represents a fundamental pillar of our security strategy. This granularity in access management allows for extremely precise control over which resources can communicate with each other, and which ports are exposed, drastically reducing the attack surface.

Each Security Group acts as a virtual firewall at the instance level, allowing or denying inbound and outbound traffic based on defined rules. This modular approach not only strengthens the intrinsic security of application data but also facilitates regulatory compliance and audit management. In the event of a compromise of a single module, the isolation guaranteed by the Security Groups prevents the spread of the attack to other parts of the platform, safeguarding the overall integrity and availability of the system.

Figure 15 - Central platform

The following paragraphs will present the architectural diagram, illustrating both the application and the infrastructure design choices.

3.2.1 eCREAM Central

eCREAM Central manages the acquisition and normalization of data from all the EDs participating in the eCREAM project.

Figure 16 - eCREAM Central

The system offers two specific HTTPS access points for acquiring the respective flows:

- Access point UC1: dedicated to receiving episode data related to use case one.
- Access point UC2: dedicated to receiving episode data related to use case two.

Both flows follow the authentication protocol outlined in the section dedicated to the Local component. The message, in addition to its informative content, is enclosed in a cryptographic envelope containing the ED identifier. The component is structured into several application modules, described below.

The 'Authentication Manager' component analyses and verifies the authentication and authorization of incoming messages, extracting the informative content and the ED identifier.

The 'Dispatcher' component, based on the ED identity obtained from the 'Authentication manager' component, activates the appropriate "ED normalization streamline".

The eCREAM model, which describes the informative content of each episode, is standardized and shared by all hospitals participating in the project. However, some entities are not normalized among the various EDs in relation to the units of measurement used. The purpose of the 'ED normalize streamline' is to standardize all elements in conformity with the eCREAM data model directives.

Figure 17 - ED normalize streamline

For each ED connected to the eCREAM system, there is an “ED normalize streamline” configuration within the central eCREAM system. Each streamline is configured to normalize all the data provided by each individual ED against the eCREAM model values. All normalized and processed data is saved within a staging database dedicated to each ED.

The ‘Data unification’ process consolidates the individual staging databases built by the normalization streamline into a single UC1 and UC2 data model.

3.2.2 Translation Manager

The Translation Manager component is thoroughly described in the two appendices of document “D6.2 PLATFORM FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS”:

- Annex 1_D62 - eCREAM Functional Specification Translation Manager

3.2.3 API

The APIs, used by the Dashboard and the Citizens’ App, are the result of the collaboration between the components illustrated in the figure. They consist of AWS services and components written in JAVA, provided by dedicated AWS EC2 virtual machines.

Figure 18 - API

The exposed services utilize the following components:

- **AWS WAF:** A managed security service by Amazon Web Services for protecting web applications and APIs from common exploits and malicious bots.
- **AWS API Gateway:** A service for creating, publishing, maintaining, monitoring, and securing HTTPS/JSON APIs.
- **Authentication Server:** Manages authentication and authorization processes.
- **Spring Boot API Services:** Responsible for service implementation.

Figure 19 - Spring Boot API Services

The following illustrates the flow of a request from a client to the Spring Boot application that implements the requested service, using AWS WAF and API Gateway, once the token acquisition procedure is complete:

- **Client (User/Application):**
 - The client application sends an HTTPS request to the public URL exposed by API Gateway, associated with a single service.
- **AWS WAF (Web Application Firewall):**

- First Line of Defense: WAF examines the HTTP/S request (headers, payload, URL, etc.) against configured rules (e.g., Managed Rules for OWASP Top 10, custom rules to block specific IPs or attack patterns).
- Decision: If the request violates a WAF rule, WAF takes the configured action (e.g., blocks the request, forwards it for a CAPTCHA challenge, or counts it). The request will not reach API Gateway.
- If the request is considered valid by WAF, it is forwarded to AWS API Gateway.
- AWS API Gateway:
 - HTTPS Endpoint: API Gateway is configured as an HTTPS terminator for the domain, handling the encryption/decryption of HTTPS traffic with clients.
- API Gateway processes the request:
 - Authentication/Authorization: API Gateway verifies the user's identity and permissions through the Authentication Server service.
 - Transformation: It associates the user information obtained from the Authentication Server service with the request.
 - Routing: It forwards the request to the configured backend integration.
- Backend Integration (your Spring Boot applications on EC2):
 - API Gateway is configured to point to the EC2 instances where the Spring Boot applications are running. Integration can occur via:
 - Directly to EC2 instances (IP/DNS): Less common option for scalable architectures, but API Gateway can point directly to an IP or DNS of an EC2 instance.
- Spring Boot Applications on EC2:
 - The Spring Boot applications receive the request (already filtered by WAF and handled by API Gateway).
 - They process the business logic and return a response.
- Return to Client:
 - The response follows the reverse path: from Spring Boot to API Gateway, and then from API Gateway to the client. API Gateway can also transform the response before sending it to the client.

3.2.4 ED-EHR

Detailed information on the Back-end component of the ED-EHR system is available in the document "D3.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN". The description of the "client" components comes from that document. The back-end layer consists of multiple service modules designed to handle specific business logic and data management tasks. Among these are core services, which provide essential and cross-cutting functionalities for the platform. These are the EHR building blocks and include components for user authentication, permission management, and configuration settings. In addition to the core services, there are specialized modules responsible for orchestrating patient flow and tracking the patient's status throughout their stay in the ED. These services ensure that the patient's journey is monitored in real-time, from initial check-in to discharge. Critical data, such as medical records and patient identification information, is managed and securely stored by dedicated services.

The following diagram, described in detail in the document "D3.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN", provides a schematic representation of the EHR software architecture, highlighting the front-end and back-end layers and how their modules are grouped according to their type and role within the system.

Figure 20 - ED-EHR Architectural design

From a delivery platform architecture point of view, two components are considered:

- Database PostgreSQL:
 - Dedicated component for informational data storage. Its ability to handle both structured and semi-structured data seamlessly, thanks to its support for JSON. This flexibility allows developers to manage a wide range of healthcare data types, from highly structured patient records to more flexible formats like clinical notes, all within a single platform.
- NodeJS:
 - Dedicated Server component for delivering the *Fastif* framework, a web framework highly focused on providing the best developer experience with the least overhead and a powerful plugin architecture.

3.2.5 Propensity to hospitalization algorithm

The current module provides access to an R environment for designing the hospital admission propensity algorithm using the RStudio server (Open-Source version).

RStudio Server offers a powerful and user-friendly web interface that allows users to work with R directly from their web browser, eliminating the need to install R and RStudio on every single local machine. RStudio offers a web-based integrated development environment (IDE); RStudio Server replicates the RStudio desktop IDE experience directly in the browser. End-users can:

- **Write and execute R code:** With an advanced code editor that includes syntax highlighting, autocompletion, and debugging.
- **Manage projects:** Organize work into projects, facilitating collaboration and reproducibility.
- **Visualize data and graphs:** Monitor variables in the environment, inspect dataframes, and view plots generated by R code.
- **Access the R console:** Interact directly with the R engine.
- **Manage packages:** Install and load R packages from CRAN or other repositories.

Using RStudio Server, users will access the UC1 database in the central domain.

A replication mechanism is used to maintain independence in managing the database for the propensity-to-hospitalization algorithm. This process involves copying the main UC1 database into a read-only database, called “Snapshot UC1”.

The proposed architectural solution leverages **Read Replicas**, a native and highly performant feature offered by the AWS RDS (Relational Database Service) component. This technological choice ensures scalability, availability, and optimal performance for data processing.

AWS RDS Read Replicas differ from a manual MySQL replication setup on EC2 instances due to a series of intrinsic advantages:

- **Automatic Management:** AWS RDS autonomously handles the complete management of the replica, including provisioning, patching, backups, and monitoring.
- **Simplified Scalability:** It’s possible to scale read capabilities horizontally by easily adding new Read Replicas. This allows distributing the read workload across multiple instances, improving overall system performance, especially in scenarios with high volumes of read queries.
- **Availability and Resilience:** In case of a malfunction of the primary (master) instance, Read Replicas can be promoted to master instances, ensuring a quick resumption of service and minimizing downtime.
- **Workload Isolation:** The use of Read Replicas allows isolating the read workload from the write workload. Write operations occur on the primary instance, while read queries are directed to the replicas. This prevents intensive read operations from negatively impacting the performance of critical write operations.

In this architectural context, data processing related to UC1 is separated from data processing for the specific purposes of the propensity-to-hospitalization algorithm. This separation of workloads and the use of Read Replicas ensures that:

- Read operations related to UC1 - Snapshot UC1 - benefit from high performance and low latency, even during traffic peaks.
- Data integrity and consistency are always guaranteed, thanks to continuous synchronization between the master instance and the replicas.
- The system is robust and scalable, capable of adapting to growing data processing and access needs.

3.3 Physical Deployment Architecture

This section is dedicated to the detailed description of the physical architecture that supports the delivery of the central platform components. This architecture has been designed to ensure scalability, resilience, and optimal performance, fully leveraging the potential of modern cloud infrastructures.

The following figure schematically illustrates the arrangement of physical resources.

The foundations of this architecture are based entirely on the application and infrastructure elements provided by the **Amazon Web Services (AWS)** delivery platform. The choice of AWS is not accidental, but is dictated by its proven reliability, the wide range of services offered, and its ability to support enterprise workloads with high security and availability requirements.

Specifically, the architecture leverages the following key AWS services:

- **Amazon EC2 (Elastic Compute Cloud):** For providing scalable computational capacity in the cloud, hosting containers and server-side applications.
- **Amazon RDS (Relational Database Service):** For managing relational databases, ensuring high availability and scalability for transactional data.
- **Amazon VPC (Virtual Private Cloud):** For creating an isolated and customized virtual network within AWS, ensuring security and resource segmentation.
- **AWS Lambda:** For running serverless code, optimizing costs and managing event-driven functions.
- **AWS EBS:** A high-performance, scalable, and easy-to-use block storage service specifically designed for use with **Amazon EC2 (Elastic Compute Cloud)** instances, AWS virtual machines.
- **AWS API Gateway:** Is a fully managed Amazon Web Services that acts as a “front door” for your backend applications, APIs, and serverless workloads. It simplifies the process for developers to publish, maintain, monitor, secure, and run APIs at any scale.
- **AWS WAF:** (Web Application Firewall) is a fully managed security service offered by Amazon Web Services. Its main purpose is to protect your web applications or APIs from common web exploits and bots that could affect availability, compromise security, or consume excessive resources. AWS WAF is designed to mitigate known and common web application attacks, often included in the **OWASP Top 10** list.

Figure 21 - Physical Deployment Architecture

The following figure visually illustrates the mapping between the architectural design and the physical deployment diagram; a detailed description follows. The components of the delivery diagram are mapped to the architectural ones of eCREAM, described in detail in the previous paragraphs. The visual mapping between the architectural design and the physical deployment is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 22 - Visual mapping between the architectural design and the physical deployment

3.3.1 eCREAM Central

Dedicated AWS resources are provided to the application components for delivering the eCREAM central solution, as shown in the figure.

Figure 23 - AWS eCREAM Central

All software components listed in paragraph 3.2.1 will be provided via a dedicated AWS EC2 instance. This architectural choice ensures an isolated and scalable environment for each component, allowing optimal resource management and increased security.

The use of dedicated instances facilitates the implementation of granular security policies and the controlled application of patches and updates, minimizing the impact on other platform components.

This strategy aims to maximize the reliability and maintainability of the entire architecture.

The dedicated AWS EC2 instance will be characterized by the following parameters:

vCPU	Memory (GiB)	Storage
4	32	Only EBS : 100GiB

3.3.2 Clinical data storage

All persistence components, including the staging databases for individual ED and the two databases related to the eCREAM UC1 and UC2, will be provided through the AWS RDS managed component.

Figure 24 - Clinical data storage

The following are the backup, encryption, and security functionalities used in RDS instances to ensure data protection and integrity.

RDS automatically manages database backups. Complete snapshots of the storage volume are taken, and transaction logs (write-ahead logs) are retained. This combination allows for point-in-time recovery of the database, restoring it to a specific second within the backup retention period (up to 35 days).

Encryption at rest will be enabled for the DB instance via AWS Key Management Service (KMS). This means that all data on the DB instance’s storage volume, logs, snapshots, and read replicas will be automatically encrypted. This implies that data will be protected even in the event of physical access to the storage. Furthermore, RDS supports encryption in transit (or "in-flight") using SSL/TLS, ensuring the protection of communications between the application and the DB instance from interception. This scenario ensures data security both at rest and in transit.

The RDS instance runs within an Amazon Virtual Private Cloud (VPC), allowing the database to be isolated in a defined virtual network. Using appropriate Security Group and Network ACL configurations, the IP addresses and EC2 instances that can connect to the database will be specified.

AWS RDS complies with numerous global security standards and certifications, such as SOC 1, 2, and 3, ISO 27001, HIPAA, and GDPR. The characteristics of the RDS component used are illustrated below.

Model	vCPU	Memory (GiB)	EBS Burst Bandwidth (Mbps)	Network Performance (Gbps)
db.t4g.large	2	8	Up to 2.780	Up to 5

3.3.3 ED-EHR

Dedicated AWS resources are provided to the application components for delivering the ED-EHR solution, as shown in the figure.

Figure 25 - AWS ED-EHR solution

The PostgreSQL application persistence component will be deployed within an AWS managed service for PostgreSQL RDS **db.t4g.medium** DBMS management, characterized by the data shown in the following table.

Model	vCPU	Memory (GiB)	EBS Burst Bandwidth (Mbps)	Network Performance (Gbps)
db.t4g.medium	2	4	Up to 2.085	Up to 5

A rigorous access security policy will be meticulously enforced on the central component to guarantee that access to the Amazon RDS is granted solely from the designated application component. This application component is specifically engineered to deliver the backend functionalities of the ED-EHR system. Access will be exclusively facilitated through a dedicated AWS Security Group, which will act as a virtual firewall controlling inbound and outbound traffic to the RDS instance. This stringent measure ensures a secure and isolated communication channel, preventing unauthorized access and maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of sensitive patient data within the ED-EHR system. This robust security architecture is a critical element in safeguarding patient information and adhering to industry best practices and regulatory compliance standards for healthcare data.

The back-end component, a NodeJS application, will be deployed on a dedicated AWS EC2 virtual machine. This VM will be part of the same security group as the previously mentioned RDS component.

The AWS EC2 instance will be characterized by the following parameters:

vCPU	Memory (GiB)	Storage
4	32	Only EBS : 100GiB

3.3.4 Translation Manager

Dedicated AWS resources are provided to the application components for delivering the Translation Manager solution, as shown in the figure.

Figure 26 - AWS Translation Manager

The Translation Manager application consists of a WEB module delivered through an Apache Tomcat server and a persistence management module delivered by a MySQL DBMS server.

The MySQL DBMS persistence component will be deployed within an AWS-managed service for MySQL RDS **db.t4g.small** DBMS management, characterized by the data shown in the following table.

Model	vCPU	Memory (GiB)	EBS Burst Bandwidth (Mbps)	Network Performance (Gbps)
db.t4g.small	2	2	Up to 2.085	Up to 5

The Apache Tomcat server is delivered within a dedicated virtual machine. The dedicated AWS EC2 instance will be characterized by the following parameters:

vCPU	Memory (GiB)	Storage
2	16	Only EBS : 50GiB

3.3.5 API

Figure 27 - API EC2 Virtual machine

All custom components, namely the Spring Boot applications, will be installed on an EC2 virtual machine with the following parameters.

vCPU	Memory (GiB)	Storage
4	32	Only EBS : 100GiB

The AWS managed services, AWS WAF and AWS API Gateway, will be configured as described in paragraph 3.2.3.

All APIs will be exposed on a subdomain of ecreamproject.eu, where the HTTPS certificate will be installed on the AWS API Gateway component.

3.3.6 Propensity to hospitalization algorithm

The RStudio server will be installed on a dedicated AWS EC2 virtual machine. A MySQL database will be exposed to ensure secure and controlled access to the 'Snapshot UC1' Database data. This MySQL database will be hosted on a central RDS instance, ensuring high availability, scalability, and automated database management.

Access to the database will be provided through a dedicated MySQL account, configured with appropriate credentials and permissions to limit access only to the necessary data, thereby ensuring the security and integrity of the information.

Figure 28 - RStudio server

To accurately manage access security to the RStudio service and data on 'Snapshot UC1', the AWS components will be subjected to a dedicated security group configured with appropriate access rules. Access to the RStudio WEB component will be protected via personal username/password and exclusive access on configured IPs.

The MySQL 'Snapshot UC1' DBMS will be deployed within an AWS-managed service for MySQL RDS db.t4g.large DBMS management, characterized by the data shown in the following table.

Model	vCPU	Memory (GiB)	EBS Burst Bandwidth (Mbps)	Network Performance (Gbps)
db.t4g.large	2	8	Up to 2.780	Up to 5

The RStudio server is delivered within a dedicated virtual machine. The dedicated AWS EC2 instance will be characterized by the following parameters:

vCPU	Memory (GiB)	Storage
4	8	Only EBS : 50GiB

3.3.7 NLP

The current NLP approach adopted in the eCREAM project is described in the deliverable "D1.4 - Performance of NLP models, Cycle I" of the eCREAM project.

D1.4 outlines the elements necessary to set up the NLP component within Work Package 1 of the eCREAM project.

Large Language Models (LLMs) have recently emerged as powerful tools for extracting information from textual documents thanks to their powerful architectures and training procedures that enable them to derive structured knowledge from unstructured natural language text. Leveraging their exceptional capabilities in understanding and generating text, LLMs have been integrated into various NLP tasks, often adopting a generative paradigm.

The landscape of LLMs is continuously evolving with new, more powerful models released every month.

Input and output of the module are defined as follows:

- Input is a single note in txt format and a CRF schema to be filled. The schema provides a set of items, and on each item, constraints are defined on the possible values (e.g., "yes", "no", "unknown", "numerical").
- Output is a JSON file with the CRF structure filled, respecting the constraints on the values (e.g., if the constraint is "yes", variants generated by the model, such as "certainly", are not allowed even if

with the same meaning). If the value must be extracted from the text needs to respect the constraints (e.g., a number).

An analysis and evaluation activity of different NLP models is underway. Once this phase is concluded and the quantitative properties of the selected model are defined, it will be possible to identify the most suitable architecture for delivery.

The infrastructure for delivering NLP services is currently under evaluation. Various options are being analysed, both internal and external to the AWS platform.

Currently, two solutions are being considered:

- RUNPOD GPU H100 SX VRAM 80GB on 20 vCPU, 188GB.
- Trn1 di Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) instance, based on AWS Trainium chip.

Conclusion on the platform functional requirements

The eCREAM platform architecture is an advanced technological solution designed to ensure scalability, security, and maintainability. Its modular, cloud-native design supports incremental system evolution and adaptability to emerging clinical and organizational requirements. The distributed architecture, composed of eCREAM Local and eCREAM Central, enables efficient collection, normalization, and analysis of clinical data, supporting two strategic use cases: predictive modelling for hospital admission risk (UC1) and operational dashboards for institutional users and citizens (UC2). Integration with international standards (e.g., HL7 FHIR), the adoption of secure communication protocols (HTTPS, HMAC), and deployment on AWS infrastructure ensure interoperability, data protection, and regulatory compliance, including GDPR.

The platform is also designed to interoperate with external ecosystems, such as the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP), in line with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), enabling responsible data sharing and collaborative research.

Annexes

Annex 1_D6.3- eCREAM Augmentation of the data dictionary

Annex 1

Augmentation of the data dictionary eCREAM

Project: eCREAM

enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

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Summary

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2. Augmentation of the data dictionary eCREAM model.....	3

1. Purpose of the document

This document contains the extension of the data dictionary, including the additional data resulting from the interaction with the NLP model.

2. Augmentation of the data dictionary eCREAM model.

During the training phase of the NLP model, annotations are conducted based on the questions included in the CRF (Case Report Form), classifying the information as *present*, *not present*, or *not detected*. This allows the model, once integrated into the UC1 in eCREAM Central Platform workflow for transforming free text into structured data, to return a normalized response of “yes”, “no”, or “not detectable”, with “not detectable” as the default value when no evidence is found.

Free-text or short descriptive answers are not expected: the output may only include binary values (*yes/no*) or, where applicable, numeric values. If such numeric values are already available as native structured data, these are considered more reliable and therefore prioritized over values extracted from free text.

SUBSET NAME	NLP Text Category	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
episode				episode	Mandatory	Admission of the patient to the ED.	
		organizationCode	Unique numeric identification code that is used to identify a hospital within health care and administrative systems.	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 12 characters.	30987
		emergencyDepartmentId	ID of ED (general, obstetrics, ophthalmology....)	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 20 characters.	
		episodeId	identification ED patient's admission	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 20 characters.	2024123455
		edArrivalDateTime	Date and time of arrival at the ED	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		sex	Gender of the patient.	String	Optional	Allowed values: 1 for Male, 2 for Female, 9 for Not Specified	1
		age	The age in years of the patient.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 3 characters	42
triage		arrivalModeCode	How the patient arrived at the ED: e.g. by ambulance dispatched by pre-hospital emergency service (EMS), by helicopter dispatched by EMS, transferred from an ED of another Hospital, Self-presented/by their own means	String	Optional	E.r.: 1: Ambulance from 112 , 2: Ambulance rom another hospital, 3: Autonomous (by own means), 4: Other (fire department, military ambulance, etc.), 5: Not known. The Hospital has to provide a table containing the description of each code.	3
		triageDateTime	Date and time of triage.	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23

	TRIAGE	triagePriority	Priority level code assigned to the patient.	String	Optional	Allowed values: Code - Description: 1,2,3,4,5,6, X (Not performed) The Hospital has to provide a table containing the description of each code.	2
		triageNotes	The field contains triage notes including medications and drugs taken at home, allergies, known pathologies collected at triage etc.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters	Patient presented with severe chest pain and difficulty breathing. History of heart disease.
		mainClinicalProblem	Main clinical problem and symptoms detected during the triage evaluation	String	Optional	E.g.: 1 - Coma, 2 - Acute neurological syndrome, 3 - Other nervous system symptoms, 4 - Abdominal pain, 5 - Chest pain, 6 - Dyspnoea, etc. The Hospital has to provide a table containing the description of each code.	14
		secondaryClinicalProblem	Description of Secondary clinical problem and symptoms detected during the triage evaluation.	String	Optional		
turnaroundTime			The turnaround time (the time taken for ambulance crew to handover the patient and restock the vehicle, so it is ready to attend another call) is taken from the time of arrival of the ambulance at the receiving hospital to the time the ambulance "clears" becomes available. This includes the time taken to wait to handover a patient to the care of the hospital staff plus any additional time they spend at hospital.	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	

pathAssignmentList				array	Optional	Filled with as many elements of the pathAssignment entity as the path assignment. If, for example, a patient first referred to an Ophthalmic Fast-Track pathway and later referred to the Low Complexity Area pathway, there must be two elements of the assignmentPathwayPS entity-one for the Ophthalmic Fast-Track and the other for the Low Complexity Area pathway	
		idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		edPathAssignmentDateTime	Date and hour of the path assignment of the patient	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	
		pathCode	ED path identification code	String	Optional	E.g.: 1. High complexity area; 2. Low complexity area; 3. Paediatric fast-track; 4. Ophthalmologic fast-track	
revaluationList			List of re-evaluations of the patient's triage/priority level	array	Optional		
		idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		revaluationTime	Date and hour of the re-evaluation of the patient's triage/priority level	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		newPriorityLevel	New priority level code assigned to the patient	String	Optional	Allowed values: Code - Description: 1,2,3,4,5,6, X (Not performed). The Hospital must provide a table containing the description of each code.	2
anamnesis	ANAMNESIS		Patient's medical history information. The taking of a patient's personal medical history	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters	The patient reports a recent onset of persistent cough with yellowish-green sputum, low-grade fever, and fatigue. No history of recent travel or exposure to sick individuals. Non-smoke. No known respiratory conditions.

homeBasedTherapy	HOMEBASED THERAPY		Patient's home based therapy.	String	Optional	Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	The patient has been prescribed a 10-day course of antibiotics (Amoxicillin 500mg, twice daily) for a confirmed bacterial infection. Patient advised to complete the full course and follow up if symptoms persist or worsen. Education provided on proper medication administration and potential side effects.
medicalVisitsList			List of patient's medical visits.	array	Optional	Filled with as many elements of the medical Visits entity as there are patient visits.	
	MEDICALVISIT	idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeMedicalVisit	Date and time of doctor's taking on of the patient,	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		medicalVisitOutcome	Field filed with the outcome of visit.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	The patient presented with persistent abdominal pain and nausea. Physical examination revealed tenderness in the right lower quadrant. Laboratory tests ordered for complete blood count and abdominal ultrasound scheduled for further evaluation. Prescribed pain medication and advised on dietary modifications. Follow-up appointment scheduled in one week.
nursingCareStart			Date and time of the start of nursing care for the patient	String	Optional	Date and time of the start of nursing care for the patient Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	
imagingTestList			List of patient's imaging test.	array	Optional	Filled with as many elements of the imaging test entity as there are imaging test.	
		requestId	Field constructed from the concatenation between the ED event (episodeID) and the request number. The request number is generated by the ED system when the exam is requested (booked)	String	Mandatory	It is a unique value. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 40 characters.	2024123455_122359

		on an external system (RIS, LIS; other EHR).				
	idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
	dateTimeRequestImagingTest	Date and time of the request for imaging the test.	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeImagingTestExecution	Date and time of the execution of the imaging test.	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
	dateTimeImagingTestReport	Date and time of the imaging test report	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:15:23
	imagingTestCode	Code of the imaging test	String	Optional	coded field with imaging test. If Dyspnoea: US, Head/neck CT, Chest CT, Chest Rx, if TLoC: Brain CT scan, Brain MRI, US cardiac, Chest CT scan, Pulmonary scintigraphy, Gastroscopy, Abdomen CT scan It is necessary to receive the decoding table.	77723
	imagingTestReportText	Report of the imaging tests (CT, CR, etc.).	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	Clear lung fields with no signs of consolidation or infiltrates. No evidence of fractures or abnormalities. Normal cardiac silhouette.
labTestList		List of patient's lab test.	array	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTestExecution entity as there are imaging tests.	
	requestId	Field constructed from the concatenation between the ED event (episodeID) and the request number. The request number is generated by the ED system when the exam is requested (booked) on an external system (RIS, LIS; other EHR).	String	Mandatory	It is a unique value. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 40 characters.	2024123455_122359

LAB	idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
	labTestCode	Code of the LabTest	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 40 characters. The Hospital must provide a table containing the description of each code	
	labTestDescription	Description of the LabTest.	String	Optional	coded field with description of the laboratory test. If Dyspnoea: pH, PaO2, PaCO2, HCO3, Lactates, Haemoglobin, Platelets, Leukocytes, C Reactive Protein, bloodGlucose, bloodSodium, bloodPotatium, Creatinine, Transaminases, INR, Troponin, BNP, DDimer, SARSCoV2swabTest if TLoC: Lactates, Haemoglobin, Platelets, Leukocytes, CReactiveProtein, bloodGlucose, bloodSodium, bloodPotatium, bloodCalcium, Creatinine, Transaminases, INR, Troponin, BNP, DDimer, CreatineKinase, BloodAlcohol, BloodDrug, UrineDrug	glucose
	dateTimeLabTestRequest	Date and time of the request for the lab test	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeLabTestExecution	Date and time of the lab test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
	labTestResults	Result of the lab test.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 20 characters.	123
	unitOfMeasureLabTest	Unit of measure for the result.	String	Mandatory Conditional	if NumericResults is valued. Allowed values, for example: mg/dL, g/dL, U/L, mmol/L, %, 10^12/L, 10^9/L, pg, fL, U/L, ratio, sec, INR	mg/dL
	otherTestList	List of patient's other test.	array	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTestExecution entity as there are imaging tests.	
	requestId	Field constructed from the concatenation between the ED event (episodeID) and the request number. The request number is generated by the ED system when the exam is requested (booked) on an external system (RIS, LIS; other EHR).	String	Mandatory	It is a unique value. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 40 characters.	2024123455_122333356

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	OTHERTEST	idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeRequestOtherTest	Date and time of the request other test	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		dateTimeOtherTestExecution	Date and time of the other test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
		dateTimeOtherTestReport	Date and time of the other test report	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:15:23
		otherTestCode	Code of the other test	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters. The Hospital must provide a table containing the description of each code.	532
		otherTestReportText	Filed reporting the results of the other tests (ECG, EEG, gastroscopy etc.).	String	Optional	Field filed reporting the results of the other tests (ECG, EEG, gastroscopy etc.).	ECG waveform within normal limits
vitalParameterList			List of patient vital signs.	array	Optional	List of patient vital signs. Populated with as many elements of the "vitalParameters" entity as there are patient data collections.	
		idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeDetection	Vital signs monitoring star date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	2022-06-22T15:15:23
		systolicPressure	Systolic pressure a triage	String	Optional	String value from 0 to 3 digits, unit of measure mmHg	100
		diastolicPressure	Diastolic pressure a triage.	String	Optional	String value from 0 to 3 digits, unit of measure mmHg	120
		heartRate	Heart rate at triage.	String	Optional	String value from 0 to 3 digits, unit of measure Bpm	75
		respiratoryRate	Respiratory rate at triage.	String	Optional	String value from 0 to 2 digits, unit of measure breaths/minute	18
		bodyTemperature	Body temperature at triage.	String	Optional	String value (2 digits, 1 digit after the separator) unit of measure degrees Celsius	38.3
levelConsciousness	level of consciousness	String	Optional	The AVPU scale (Alert, Voice, Pain, Unresponsive) to measure and record the patient's level of consciousness (4 levels: AVPU). Allowed values: 1 – Alert, 2 – Voice, 3 – Pain, 4 - Unresponsive	2		

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	VITALPARAMETERS	spO2	Oxygen saturation detected at triage	String	Optional	String value to 2 digits	95
		vitalParametersText	Field used alternatively or in addition to compiling structured data. Contains list of vital Signs or clinical examination.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters.	Heart Rate: 98 bpm Respiratory Rate: 20
nursingCareNotesList			List of nursing care of the patient.	array	Optional	Nursing care of the patient.	
	NURSINGACARENOTES	idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeNote	Date and time of nurse's taking on of the patient	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	2022-06-22T1:13:23
		nursingNote	Field filled with nursing notes.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	Patient received prompt percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI) for acute myocardial infarction. Vital signs monitored closely for the first 6 hours post-procedure. No complications observed. Patient remained stable and comfortable. Provided education on post-PPCI care and scheduled follow-up appointments.
clinicalDiaryList			Information regarding the patient's clinical diary	array	Optional		
		idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeClinicalDiary	Date and time of filling of the clinical diary	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	

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	CLINICALDIARY	clinicalDiary	Field that contains clinical care data and treatment	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	Patient admitted with a history of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) exacerbation. Received nebulized bronchodilators and systemic corticosteroids. Respiratory distress improved over the next 24 hours. Continued close monitoring of oxygen saturation and respiratory rate. Introduced physiotherapy sessions for airway clearance. Patient responding well to treatment. Daily assessments scheduled to track progress.
medicalProcedureList			List of medical procedures (specific surgical, medical, or diagnostic interventions) in ED	array	Optional		
		idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeRequestMedicalProcedure	Date and time of the medical procedure request	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		dateTimeExecutionMedicalProcedure	Date and time of the medical procedure execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		medicalProcedureCode	Code of the medical procedure	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters. The Hospital must provide a table containing the description of each code.	318
specialistConsultancyList			List of patient's specialist consultancy.	array	Optional	Specialist patient consultations. Filled with as many consultations as there are consultations performed.	
		requestId	Field constructed from the concatenation between the ED event (episodeID) and the request number. The request number is generated by the ED system when the exam is requested (booked) on an external system (RIS, LIS; other EHR).	String	Mandatory	It is a unique value. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 40 characters.	2024123455_3556

	SPECIALISTCONSULTANCY	idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		consultancyType	Contains the type of consultancy requested.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 50 characters.	Cardiology Consultation
		dateTimeSpecialistConsultancy	Date and time of patient specialist consultancy	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss"	2022-06-22T15:15:23
		reportTextSpecialistConsultancy	Filled in field reporting the outcome of the specialist consultancy.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	The patient with a history of hypertension and chest pain underwent a thorough cardiac evaluation. ECG and echocardiogram performed, revealing no significant abnormalities. Recommended lifestyle modifications, continued antihypertensive medication, and scheduled a follow-up visit in three months.
pharmaceuticalTherapyList			List of pharmaceutical therapy prescription and administration.	array	Optional		
		idObject	An identifier of an object that can have multiplicity and that uniquely identifies it.	String	Optional		
		dateTimeTherapyPrescription	Pharmaceutical therapy administration - date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		dateTimeTherapyAdministration	Pharmaceutical therapy administration - date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		therapyType	Type of therapy administered.	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 200 characters.	34563
respiratorySupportList			List of respiratory support.	array	Optional		
		startTimeRespiratorySupport	Respiratory support starts date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		endTimeRespiratorySupport	Respiratory support end date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:17:32

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monitoringList			List of monitoringList.	array	Optional		
		startTimeMonitoring	Monitoring start date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		endTimeMonitoring	Monitoring end date and hour	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:17:32
discharge			List final diagnosis. Populated with as many elements of the finalDiagnosisList entity as the final diagnoses.	Discharge Element	Optional		
		dischargeDecisionDateTime	Date and time of the admission/transfer to another hospital/discharge decision, in case the patient has to wait for a bed or a transfer to another hospital (admission).	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		dischargeDateTime	Date and time of patient discharge from the ER.	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		modeOfExit	Mode of exit (admitted/transferred/deceased/voluntary abandonment)	String	Optional	Allowed values: 1- if admitted, 2 - if transferred, 3 - if decease,4 - if voluntary abandonment.	3
		diagnosisAtEDDischarge	Diagnosis at the end of ED hospitalisation	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	OTHER CHEST PAIN

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	DISCHARGE	dischargeNotes	Field filled with discharge notes, included clinical ED Outcome, ED Discharge Care Plan, ED Discharging Pharmacological Therapy and clinical Condition at Discharge	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	The patient presented with symptoms of pneumonia and received appropriate treatment during their hospital stay. Clinical condition has significantly improved, and vital signs are stable. The patient is discharged home with a prescription for antibiotics, analgesics, and instructions for continued care. Advised to follow up with the primary care physician in one week for further evaluation and monitoring. Provided education on signs and symptoms warranting immediate medical attention. Patient and family informed and engaged in the discharge plan.
obsUnit			Set of information relating to the patient's presence in the Obs Unit	Observation Unit element	Optional		
		decisionObsUnit	Date and time of decision to transfer to Short Stay Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		transferObsUnit	Date and time of transfer to Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
		exitObsUnit	Date and time of exit from ED/Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH: mm: ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
NLP History taking							
		pregnancy	Reports if the patient is pregnant	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
		historyAllergy	Report the patient's allergies	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
		historyRecentTrauma	Reports patient's recent trauma	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
		chronicPulmonaryDisease	Reports patient's chronic pulmonary disease	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic /not detectable	
		activeNeoplasia	Reports patient's active neoplasia	String	Optional	allowed values: certainly active/certainly not active/possibly active /not detectable	

	chronicDialysis	Report if the patient is undergoing dialysis	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic /not detectable	
	immunosuppression	Reports patient's immunosuppression	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	palliativeCare	Reports if the patient is in palliative care	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	neuropsychiatricDisorders	Reports patient's neuropsychiatric disorders	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	polyPharmacologicalTherapy	Reports if the patient is taking pharmacological polytherapy	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	problematicFamilyContext	Reports if the patient has family problems	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	needCaregiver	Reports if the patient need but absence of a caregiver	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	Homelessness	Reports if the patient is homelessness	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	livingAlone	Reports if the patient lives alone	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	historyDrugAbuse	Report if the patient has used drugs	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	historyAlcoholAbuse	Report if the patient has used alcohol	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	presencePacemaker	Report if the patient has a pacemaker	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	presenceDefibrillator	Report if the patient has a defibrillator	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	cardioPulmonaryResuscitation	Report if the patient has had cardiopulmonary resuscitation	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	antihypertensiveTherapy	Reports if the patient is taking antihypertensive therapy	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	anticoagulantsAntiplateletTherapy	Reports if the patient is taking anticoagulants therapy	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	diagnosisCardiovascularDiseases	Report if the patient has a diagnosis of cardiovascular disease	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	diagnosisNeurodegenerativeDiseases	Report if the patient has a diagnosis of	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	

		neurodegenerative disease				
	diagnosisPeripheralNeuropathy	Report if the patient has a diagnosis of peripheral neuropathy disease	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	diagnosisChronicRespiratoryFailure	Report if the patient has chronic respiratory failure	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic /not detectable	
	diagnosisChronicCardiacFailure	Report if the patient has chronic cardiac failure	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic /not detectable	
	diagnosisChronicRenalFailure	Report if the patient has chronic renal failure	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic /not detectable	
	diagnosisChronicMetabolicFailure	Report if the patient has chronic metabolic failure	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic /not detectable	
	diagnosisDiffuseVascularDisease	Report if the patient has diagnosis diffuse vascular disease	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no detectable	
	diagnosisChronicRheumatologicDisease	Report if the patient has chronic rheumatologic disease	String	Optional	allowed values: chronic/certainly not chronic/possibly chronic/not detectable	
	prodromalSymptoms	report the presence of prodromal symptoms	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	complianceAntiepilepticTherapy	Reports if the patient is taking antiepileptic therapy already in place and compliance for antiepileptic therapy	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	durationPatientUnconsciousness	Duration of the patient's unconsciousness	String	Optional	2 levels: fast (seconds)/slow (minutes-hours/ not detectable	
	tlocDuringEffort	report TLoC during effort	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	tlocWhileSupine	indicates TLoC occurring while the patient is supine	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	firstEpisodeKnowEpilepsy	reports diagnosis of epilepsy (First episode vs. known history of epilepsy)	String	Optional	allowed values: first episode/non first episode/ not detectable	
	antiepilepticTherapyAlreadyInPlace	therapy already in place	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	drowsinessConfusionDisorientationPostcriticalState	Drowsiness, confusion, disorientation as postcritical state	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	

	paleSkin	reports the pale skin during the episode	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	eyeDeviation	reports the eye deviation during the episode	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	stiffness	reports the stiffness during the episode	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	drooling	reports the drooling during the episode	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	tonicClonicSeizures	reports if the patient is tonic clonic seizures	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	situationDescription	Situation description, like coughing, prolonged periods of straining, sudden abdominal pain, phlebotomy	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	speedRecoveredConsciousness	Speed with which the patient recovered consciousness	String	Optional	2 levels: fast (seconds)/slow (minutes-hours/ not detectable	
NLP Clinical examination						
	dementia	Patient's dementia status	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	generalConditionDeterioration	Patient's general conditions deterioration	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	levelAutonomy	Level of autonomy (mobility)	String	Optional	4 levels: allowed values: 1 if walking independently, 2 if walking with auxiliary aids, 3 if walking with physical assistance, 4 if bedridden/ Not detectable	
	levelConsciousness	The AVPU scale (Alert, Voice, Pain, Unresponsive) to measure and record the patient's level of consciousness (4 levels: AVPU).	String	Mandatory	The AVPU scale (Alert, Voice, Pain, Unresponsive) to measure and record the patient's level of consciousness (4 levels: AVPU). Allowed values: 1 – Alert, 2 – Voice, 3 – Pain, 4 - Unresponsive/ Not detectable	2
	agitation	Patient's agitation status	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	presenceDyspnea	Presence of dyspnea	String	The presence of dyspnea	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	respiratoryDistress	Patient's respiratory distress	String	Optional	allowed values: Respiratory Distress-Actual/Respiratory Distress-Previous/not detectable	
	foreignBodyAirways	Patient's foreign body airways	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	respiratoryRate	Respiratory rate at triage.	String	Optional	allowed values: RR-bradycic/RR-eupnoeic/ RR-tachypnoeic/ not detectable (vn 12-20)	

	bodyTemperature	Body temperature at triage.	String	Optional	allowed values: TC-hypothermic/TC-normothermic/TC-hyperthermic/not detectable	
	heartRate	Heart rate at triage.	String	Optional	allowed values: HR-bradycardic, HR-nomocratic, HR-tachycardic/not detectable	
	BloodPressure	Systolic pressure at triage	String	Optional	allowed values: BP-hypotensive/BP-normotensive/BP-hypertensive/not detectable. (vn 80-130 mmHg)	
	chestPain	Patient's chest pain	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	improvementDyspnea	Patient's improvement dyspnea	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	headOtherDistrictsTrauma	Head or other districts trauma	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	abIngestisPneumonia	Ab ingestis pneumonia	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	tongueBite	Tongue bite	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	furtherSeizuresInED	Further seizures in the ED	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	bloodStool	bloodStool	String	Optional	allowed values: pos/neg/not detectable	
	carotidSinusMassage	Carotid sinus massage	String	Optional	allowed values: pos/neg/not detectable	
	supineToStandingSystolicBloodPressureTest	Supine-to-standing systolic blood pressure test	String	Optional	allowed values: pos/neg/not detectable	
	ImprovementPatientConditions	Improvement of patient's conditions	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
	neurologistConsultation	Neurologist consultation	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
NLP Imaging and diagnostic test results						
	thoracicUSAnyAbnormality	Thoracic ultrasound, any abnormalities	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	ecgMonitoringAnyAbnormality	ECG Monitoring Any Abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	ecgAnyAbnormality	ECG Any Abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	eegAnyAbnormality	EEG Any Abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	headNeckCTAnyAbnormality	Head/neck CT, any abnormalities	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	chestCTAnyAbnormality	Chest CT, any abnormalities	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	chestRXAnyAbnormality	Chest Rx, any abnormalities	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	brainCTscanAnyAbnormality	brain CT scan, any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	brainMRIAnyAbnormality	Brain MRI, any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	cardiacUSAnyAbnormality	Cardiac ultrasound, any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	

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	pulmonaryScintigraphyAnyAbnormality	Pulmonary scintigraphy, any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	gastroscopy	Gastroscopy	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	abdomenCTscanAnyAbnormality	Abdomen CT scan, any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	dopplerUSdeepVeinsAnyAbnormality	Doppler ultrasound of deep veins, any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
	compressionUSAnyAbnormality	Compression ultrasound (CUS), any abnormality	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	
NLP Lab test results						
	spO2	results of SpO2	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 3 characters. value expressed as %	
	pH	result of pH	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters.	
	paO2	result of PaO2	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mmHg or alternatively in kPa. The conversion rule is as follows: mmHg = kPa × 0.1333.	
	paCO2	result of PaCO2	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mmHg or alternatively in kPa. The conversion rule is as follows: mmHg = kPa × 0.1333.	
	HCO3	result of HCO3	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mmHg or alternatively in mEq/L.	
	lactates	result of Lactates	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mmol/L or alternatively in mg/dL. The conversion rule is as follows: mmHg = kPa × 0.111.	
	hemoglobin	result of Hemoglobin	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in g/dL or alternatively in mmol/L or mg/dL. The conversion rule is as follows: g/dL = mmol/L/ 0.6206 or g/dL = mg/dL^ 0,001	
	platelets	result of Platelets	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in 1 x10 ³ /μL or alternatively in 1 x10 ⁹ /L	
	leukocytes	result of Leukocytes	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in 1 x10 ³ /μL or alternatively in 1 x10 ⁹ /L	
	cReactiveProtein	result of C-Reactive Protein	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mg/L or alternatively in mg/dL.	
	bloodSodium	result of Blood sodium	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mmol/L or alternatively in mEq/L.	
	bloodPotassium	result of Blood potassium	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mmol/L or alternatively in mEq/L.	

		bloodGlucose	result of Blood glucose	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mg/dL or alternatively in mmol/L.	
		bloodCalcium	result of Blood calcium	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mg/dL or alternatively in mmol/L.	
		serumCreatineKinase	result of Serum creatine kinase	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in U/L	
		creatinine	result of Creatinine	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mg/dL or alternatively in mmol/L.	
		transaminases	result of Transaminases	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in U/L or alternatively in ukat/L.	
		INR	result of INR	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters.	
		troponin	result of Troponin	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mcg/L or alternatively in ng/L or pg/mL .	
		bnp	result of BNP / NT-pro-BNP	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in pg/mL or alternatively in pmol/L or pmol/dL.	
		ddimer	result of D-dimer	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mg/L or alternatively in ng/mL. The conversion rule is as follows: mg/L = ng/mL/1000	
		bloodAlcohol	result of Blood alcohol	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mg/L	
		bloodDrugDosage	result of Blood drug dosage	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in mcg/mL and depends on the drug.	
		urineDrugTest	result of Urine drug test	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 5 characters. Value expressed in ng/mL and depends on the drug.	
		sARSCoV2swabTest	result of SARS-CoV-2 swab test	String	Optional	allowed values: pos/neg/not detectable	
NLP Treatment							
		thoracentesis	reports thoracentesis	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		administrationDiuretics	reports administration diuretics	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		administrationFluids	reports administration fluids	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		administrationSteroids	reports administration steroids	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		administrationBronchodilators	reports administration bronchodilators	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		administrationOxygenVentilation	reports administration ventilation	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		bloodTransfusions	reports blood transfusions	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
NLP Final diagnosis							
		finalDiagnosisSituationalSyncope	final diagnosis of syncope	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisPulmonaryEmbolism	final diagnosis of pulmonary embolism	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	

		finalDiagnosisHeartFailure	final diagnosis of heart failure	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisPneumonia	final diagnosis of Pneumonia	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisCOPDExacerbation	final diagnosis of COPD exacerbation	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisAcutePulmonaryEdema	final diagnosis of acute pulmonary edema	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisAsthmaExacerbation	final diagnosis of asthma exacerbation	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisSevereAnaemia	final diagnosis of severe Anaemia	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisArrhythmia	final diagnosis of arrhythmia	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisRespiratoryFailure	final diagnosis of respiratory failure	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisIntoxication	final diagnosis of intoxication	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisCovid19	final diagnosis of covid 19	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisInfluenzaVariousInfections	final diagnosis of Influenza and various infections	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisPneumothorax	final diagnosis of pneumothorax	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisAcuteCoronarySyndrome	final diagnosis of Acute coronary syndrome	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisEpilepticSeizure	final diagnosis of Epilepsy / epileptic seizure	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisTamponadeCardiac	final diagnosis of Cardiac tamponade	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisDissectionAortic	final diagnosis of aortic dissection	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisHemorrhage	final diagnosis of hemorrhage	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
		finalDiagnosisConcussiveHeadTrauma	final diagnosis of concussive head trauma	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/not detectable	
NLP Follow-up				followup	Optional	Indicates 30-day mortality, detects if the patient is alive or deceased	
		30DayMortality	Indicates 30-day mortality, detects if the patient is alive or deceased	String	Optional	allowed values: dead/alive/not detectable	alive